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EXCHANGE TRADED FUND IN INDIA- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS WITH MUTUAL FUND AND GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

An ETF refers to a diversified basket of securities that is traded in real time like an individual stock on exchange. Unlike regular open-ended mutual funds, ETFs can be bought and sold throughout the trading day like any other stock. An ETF is similar to an index fund, but the ETFs can invest in either all of the securities or a representative sample of the securities included in the index. Exchange-traded funds first came into existence in the USA in 1993. Importantly, the ETFs offer a one-stop exposure to a diversified basket of securities that can be traded in real time like an individual stock.

ETFs experience price changes throughout the day as they are bought and sold. Because it trades like a stock, an ETF does not have its net asset value (NAV) calculated every day like a mutual fund does. By owning an ETF, you get the diversification of an index fund as well as the ability to sell short, buy on margin and purchase as little as one share. Another advantage is that the expense ratios for most ETFs are lower than those of the average mutual fund. When buying and selling ETFs, you have to pay the same commission to your broker that you'd pay on any regular order.

The first ETF in India, the “NIFTY BEES (Nifty Benchmark Exchange Traded Scheme) based on Nifty 50 was launched in December 2001 by Benchmark Mutual Fund. It is bought and sold like any other stock on NSE and has all characteristics of an index fund. As of March 2013, there were 35 ETFs listed on NSE. The ETF based on Sensex is SPICE (Sensex Prudential ICICI Exchange Traded Fund) which was launched by -Prudential ICICI. Growth in Gold ETFs have seen a rising trend as shown in Following Figure however other ETFs have seen a decline in activity from 2007 to 2011.

These funds consistently outperformed the market index and generated higher returns. ETFs generated excess returns of 3% p.a. as against CNX NIFTY, which is the Indian equity market bench mark. Gold ETFs provided 13% excess returns as compared to the returns on the equity market and attracted large investments in the post financial crisis years. Data Envelopment Analysis ranked domestic and overseas fund of funds as efficient funds, which were floated by foreign Asset Management Companies (AMCs) and the AMCs with Joint Ventures in India. Among the foreign AMCs, Franklin Templeton was found to offer the most efficient fund. These efficient funds are found to have higher Sharpe ratios, indicating that the DEA ranking is in broad consensus with the evaluation done using Sharpe ratios. However large funds were not found to be efficient funds. This infers that the fund size does not indicate superior performance.

Introduction-

Exchange-Traded Funds (ETFs) were first introduced in USA in 1993. About 60% of trading volumes on the American Stock Exchange are reported to be from ETFs. As per the ETF landscape report released by Blackrock Inc. (a US-based AMC), ETFs have grown by 33.2%, compounded annually in the past 10 years, and 26.1% in the past five years, globally.

ETFs have been limited to broad indexes. The liquidity issue raises concerns about the spreads of ETFs. In contrast to developed markets, the ETF market in countries such as India is dominated by retail investors. Hence, securities regulators are even more inclined to be conservative in allowing complicated products. In order to trade ETFs in India, investors need demat/broking accounts and many Indian investors do not have these accounts and therefore do not consider ETFs. Banks play a large role in the Indian financial markets and are the biggest distributors. They find it easier to sell open-end mutual funds that do not require demat accounts. They also do not want to be seen as selling stock market products for the fear of additional regulation and scrutiny.

In essence, ETFs trade like stocks and therefore offer a degree of flexibility unavailable with traditional mutual funds. Specifically, investors can trade ETFs throughout the trading day as in stocks. In comparison, in a traditional mutual fund, investors can purchase units only at the fund's NAV, which is published at the end of each trading day. In fact, investors cannot purchase ETFs at the closing NAV. This difference gives rise to an important advantage of Comparison of ETFs with other mutual funds.

S.No	Name of ETFs	S.No	Name of ETFs
1	Motilal MOST Shares NASDAQ 100 ETF	28	Edelweiss ETS - Nifty (Nifty EES)
2	IIFL Nifty ETF	29	UTI Nifty Exchange Traded Fund
3	GS Gold BeES	30	GS Liquid BeES
4	IDBI Gold Exchange Traded Fund	31	Motilal MOST Shares Midcap 100 ETF
5	UTI Gold Exchange Traded Fund	32	SBI - ETF Nifty Next 50
6	Religare Invesco Gold ETF	33	GS Shariah BeES
7	SBI - ETF Gold	34	GS Junior BeES
8	LIC NOMURA G-Sec LTE Fund - RP (G)	35	Motilal Oswal MOST Shares Gold ETF
9	Birla Sun Life Gold ETF (G)	36	ICICI Prudential CNX 100 ETF
10	Kotak Gold ETF	37	SBI - ETF Sensex
11	Axis Gold ETF	38	Birla Sun Life Nifty ETF
12	ICICI Pru Gold ETF	39	R*Shares Dividend ETF
13	HDFC Gold Exchange Traded Fund	40	R*Shares Nifty ETF
14	Quantum Gold Fund	41	R*shares CNX 100 ETF
15	R*Shares Gold ETF	42	Kotak Nifty ETF
16	Can Gold Exchange Traded Fund	43	ICICI Prudential Nifty ETF
17	R*shares Consumption ETF	44	ICICI Pru SPIcE Plan
18	HDFC Sensex ETF	45	SBI - ETF BSE 100
19	Kotak NV 20 ETF	46	Religare Invesco Nifty ETF
20	HDFC Nifty ETF	47	GS Nifty BeES
21	SBI - ETF Nifty 50	48	Kotak Sensex ETF
22	Edelweiss ETS - Banking	49	Motilal MOST Shares M50 ETF
23	UTI Sensex Exchange Traded Fund	50	GS Hang Seng BeES
24	GS CPSE ETF	51	R*Shares Banking ETF
25	GS Infra BeES	52	SBI - ETF Nifty Bank
26	Kotak PSU Bank ETF	53	Kotak Banking ETF
27	GS PSU Bank BeES	54	GS Bank BeES

ETFs over traditional funds: ETFs are immediately tradable and consequently, the risk of price differential between the time of investment and time of trade is substantially less in the case of ETFs.

ETFs are cheaper than traditional mutual funds and index funds in terms of fees. However, while investing in an ETF, an investor pays a commission to the broker. The tracking error of

ETFs is generally lower than traditional index funds due to the "in-kind" creation / redemption facility and the low expense ratio. This "in-kind" creation / redemption facility ensures that long-term investors do not suffer at the cost of short-term investor activity.

ETFs can be bought / sold through trading terminals anywhere across the country. Table No. 1 presents a comparative view ETFs vis-à-vis other funds.

ETFs Vs. Open Ended Funds Vs. Close Ended Funds

Parameter	Open Ended Fund	Closed Ended Fund	Exchange Traded Fund
Fund Size	Flexible	Fixed	Flexible
NAV	Daily	Daily	Real Time
Liquidity Provider	Fund itself	Stock Market	Stock Market / Fund itself
Sale Price	At NAV plus load, if any	Significant Premium / Discount to NAV	Very close to actual NAV of Scheme
Availability	Fund itself	Through Exchange where listed	Through Exchange where listed / Fund itself.
Portfolio Disclosure	Monthly	Monthly	Daily/Real-time
Uses	Equitising cash	-	Equitising Cash, Hedging, Arbitrage
Intra-Day Trading	Not possible	Expensive	Possible at low cost

ETFs are referred to as passive schemes that fund managers resort to, to avoid risk and offer low-cost options to the investors. These funds rely on an arbitrage mechanism to maintain the prices at which they trade, in line with the net asset values of their underlying portfolios.

As Exchange-Traded Funds started growing in India since 2006, the investment industry required performance analysis of this newly available financial asset. Moreover, fund selection also requires investors to analyze returns, volatility and performance of the available funds. The purpose of this paper is to empirically assess the investment

performance of Exchange-Traded Funds in India. The paper uses monthly returns of ETFs over the period 2006-2011 to analyze 82 ETFs that were floated and traded on the Indian Stock Market across various themes. The paper investigates the relationship between fund size and performance and provides useful insights for the fund managers and investors.

Performance of ETFs has been examined on the basis of their returns and risk characteristics. Performance measures include average annual returns and excess returns measured by alpha values; risks measured by standard deviation and risk-adjusted returns measured by the Sharpe ratio. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) with three inputs and two out variables was used to analyze ETF performance and generate relative efficiency ranking among the peer group of funds.

On an average in India, ETFs grew at 37% annually during 2006 -2011. These funds also generated excess returns of 3% p.a. as against CNX NIFTY, the Indian equity market's benchmark. Gold ETFs provided 13% excess returns as compared to the returns on the equity market and attracted large investments in the post financial crisis years. Data Envelopment Analysis ranked domestic and overseas fund of funds as efficient funds.

These efficient funds were floated by foreign Asset Management Companies (AMCs) and the AMCs with joint ventures in India. In India, as on 31st May 2011, there are 25 large funds which represent the most recent gold funds as well as overseas fund of funds. The efficient funds were not found to be the large funds; however, they offered higher returns and have higher Sharpe ratios. This paper, being the first research work on ETFs in India, not only contributes to academic literature but also provides insights to investment professionals about an economy that is gaining significant prominence as an emerging economy in the global investment landscape.

Advantages of ETFs

While many investors have similar outlooks, no two are exactly alike. Due to the unique structure of ETFs, all types of investors, whether retail or institutional, long-term or short-term, can use it to their advantage without being at a disadvantage to others. They allow long-term investors to diversify their portfolio at one shot at low cost and insulate them from short-term trading activity due to the unique "in-kind" creation / redemption process. They provide

liquidity for investors with a shorter-term horizon as they can trade intra-day and can have quotes near NAV during the course of trading day. As initial investment is low, retail investors find it simple and convenient to buy / sell. They facilitate FIIs, Institutions and Mutual Funds to have easy asset allocation, hedging, equitising cash at a low cost. They enable arbitrageurs to carry out arbitrage between the Cash and the Futures markets at low impact cost.

ETFs provide exposure to an index or a basket of securities that trade on the exchange like a single stock. They offer a number of advantages over traditional open-ended index funds as follows:

While redemptions of Index fund units takes place at a fixed NAV price (usually end of day), ETFs offer the convenience of intra-day purchase and sale on the Exchange, to take advantage of the prevailing price, which is close to the actual NAV of the scheme at any point in time.

They provide investors a fund that closely tracks the performance of an index throughout the day with the ability to buy/sell at any time, whereby trading opportunities that arise during a day may be better utilized. They are low cost. Unlike listed closed-ended funds, which trade at substantial premia or more frequently at discounts to NAV, ETFs are structured in a manner which allows Authorized Participants and Large Institutions to create new units and redeem outstanding units directly with the fund, thereby ensuring that ETFs trade close to their actual NAVs. ETFs are like any other index fund, wherein, subscription / redemption of units work on the concept of exchange with underlying securities instead of cash (for large deals). Since an ETF is listed on an Exchange, costs of distribution are much lower and the reach is wider. These savings in cost are passed on to the investors in the form of lower costs. Further, the structure helps reduce collection, disbursement and other processing charges.

ETFs protect long-term investors from inflows and outflows of short-term investors. This is because the fund does not incur extra transaction cost for buying/selling the index shares due to frequent subscriptions and redemptions.

Tracking error, which is divergence between the NAV of the ETF and the underlying Index, is generally observed to be low as compared to a normal index fund due to lower expenses and the unique in-kind creation / redemption process.

ETFs are highly flexible and can be used as a tool for gaining instant exposure to the equity markets, equitising cash or for arbitraging between the cash and futures market.

The first ETF in India, "Nifty BeEs (Nifty Benchmark Exchange Traded Scheme) based on Nifty 50, was launched in January 2002 by Benchmark Mutual Fund. It may be bought and sold like any other stock on NSE. Its symbol on NSE is "NIFTYBEES".

Structure of ETF

Applications of ETFs

Efficient Trading: ETFs provide investors a convenient way to gain market exposure viz. an index that trades like a stock. In comparison to a stock, an investment in an ETF index product provides a diversified exposure to the market. Depending on the index, investors may obtain exposure to countries/ markets or sectors.

Equitising Cash: Investors with idle cash in their portfolios may want to invest in a product tied to a market benchmark like an index as a temporary investment before deciding which stocks to buy or waiting for the right price.

Managing Cash Flows: Investment managers who see regular inflows and outflows may use ETFs because of their liquidity and their ability to represent the market.

Diversifying Exposure: If an investor is not sure about which particular stock to buy but likes the overall sector, investing in shares tied to an index or basket of stocks provides diversified exposure and reduces stock specific risk.

Filling Gaps: ETFs tied to a sector or industry may be used to gain exposure to new and important sectors. Such strategies may also be used to reduce an overweight or increase an underweight sector.

Shorting or Hedging: Investors who have a negative view on a market segment or specific sector may want to establish a short position to capitalize on that view. ETFs may be sold short against long stock holdings as a hedge against a decline in the market or specific sector.

Review of Literature

ETFs' Performance Across Countries

The existing evidence in the literature on performance of ETFs is mixed. While there were any papers reporting negative performance of ETFs, there were others that presented strong positive evidence about the performance of ETFs. Adjei Frederick (2009) found no significant difference between the performances of the ETFs and the S&P 500 index. He found weak evidence of performance persistence on both the half-yearly and the yearly horizons.

Johnson (2009) reported the existence of tracking errors between foreign ETFs and the underlying home index returns. Blitz David et al. (2010) investigated the performance of index mutual funds and the ETFs that are listed in Europe. They found that European index funds and ETFs underperform their benchmarks by 50 to 150 basis points per annum. William (2009) found the existence of tracking errors between foreign ETFs and the underlying home index in US.

Blitz David and Huij (2011) evaluated the performance of ETFs that provide passive exposure to global emerging markets (GEM) equities and found that GEM ETFs exhibit higher tracking error. Houweling (2011) found that treasury ETFs were able to track their benchmark but investment grade corporate bond ETFs and high yield corporate bond ETFs underperform their benchmarks. Charupat & Miu (2011) analyzed the performance of leverage ETFs, and concluded that price deviations are small among leverage ETFs and that price volatility is more, as a result of rebalancing, at the end of the day.

Patrick (2011) found that in Hong Kong the magnitude of tracking errors is negatively related to the size but positively related to the expense ratio of the ETFs. He further commented that replicating the performance of underlying securities involves more risk, since they have a higher tracking error than in the US and Australia.

On the contrary, there was equal evidence of positive performance of ETFs. Ching-Chung et.al. (2005) indicated that the Taiwanese ETF and, the Taiwan Top 50 Tracker Fund (TTT) are price efficient and trading on them produces almost identical returns to the Taiwan stock market. Joel et al. (2006) compared the risk and return performances of ETFs available for foreign markets and closed-end country funds. They found higher mean returns and Sharpe ratios for ETFs, and concluded that a passive investment strategy through ETFs is observed to be superior to an active investment strategy using closely held country funds.

Huang and Guedj (2009) investigated as to whether an Exchange-Traded Fund (ETF) is a more efficient indexing vehicle than an Open-Ended Mutual Fund (OEF). They noted that ETFs are better suited for narrower and less liquid underlying indexes, and also for investors with long investment horizons. Jack et al. (2009) indicated that the US ETFs are more likely to trade at a premium than at a discount, with comparatively large daily price fluctuations.

Gerasimos (2011) found that ETFs trade at a premium from their Net Asset Value (NAV) and the pattern of their returns can be predicted. Meric et al. (2009) reported that from October 9, 2007 to March 9, 2009, the U.S. stock market experienced the worst bear market and lost about 56% of its value during this period. They compared the performances of 38 sector index funds using the Sharpe and Treynor portfolio performance measures and found that the healthcare and consumer staples sector index funds had the best performance and the financials and home construction sector index funds had the worst performance in the October 9, 2007-March 9, 2009 bear market run.

Wong and Shum (2010) examined the performances of 15 worldwide ETFs across bearish and bullish markets over the period 1999 to 2007. They observed that ETFs always provide higher returns in a bullish market than in a bearish market. They noted from the Sharpe ratios that ETF returns are not positive and proportional to the market volatility.

Yuexiang et al. (2010) investigated the pricing efficiency of the Shanghai 50 ETF (SSE 50 ETF), the first Exchange-Traded Fund (ETF) in China. They demonstrated that ETF market

prices and their Net Asset Values are co-integrated and there is a unidirectional causality from price to NAV. They also found that the fund's prices did not closely follow the NAV during the second half of 2007, when the Chinese stock market experienced substantial volatility, reflecting sudden increased market risks as well as potential arbitrage opportunities during financial turbulences. Gerasimos (2011) found that the performance of ETFs is predictable and the return superiority is persistent in the short term level.

This mixed evidence about performance of ETFs across developed as well as emerging economies warrants and motivated the present research about the performance of ETFs in India.

There are many research papers on the Indian mutual fund (MF) industry. Sivakumar et al. (2010) observed that private players were able to mobilize greater resources in the Indian MF industry than public institutions. Jaspal Singh (2004) evaluated the performance of various mutual funds and found that ICICI prudential floated and managed by a private AMC is the best performer in India. Madhumita et al. (2008) evaluated the performance of mutual funds on the basis of rate of returns as well as risk-adjusted methods, and found that the majority of equity funds outperformed the benchmark index. Most of these studies evaluated the growth and performance of equity funds, but there is no paper on Exchange-Traded Funds in India. Hence, the focus of this paper is to investigate the growth and performance of ETFs in India.

TRADING STATISTICS OF EXCHANGE TRADED FUNDS (Etf)s IN INDIA

As of May 2011, there were 47 ETFs that offer Russian exposure, 69 ETFs offer exposure to Brazil, 160 offer exposure to China, and there are 43 India-related ETFs listed in the U.S. In May 2011, Direxion Funds filed with the SEC to introduce nine new India-related ETFs that are not leveraged. 15 Emerging Global Advisors has also filed for additional Indian ETFs with nine of them focusing on different sectors of the economy. These ETFs provide investors another option to obtain easy exposure to foreign markets. ETFs trading in emerging markets are typically of the vanilla type with synthetic or leveraged ETFs not being allowed in most emerging markets. One of the issues in emerging markets is that only stocks in broad based indexes tend to be liquid; therefore, ETFs have been limited to broad indexes. The liquidity issue raises concerns about the spreads of ETFs. In contrast to developed markets, the ETF market in countries such as India is dominated by retail investors. Hence, securities regulators are even more inclined to be conservative in allowing complicated products. In order to trade

ETFs in India, investors need demat/broking accounts and many Indian investors do not have these accounts and therefore do not consider ETFs. Banks play a large role in the Indian financial markets and are the biggest distributors. They find it easier to sell open-end mutual funds that do not require demat accounts. They also do not want to be seen as selling stock market products for the fear of additional regulation and scrutiny. Past four years India's Trading statistics of Exchange Traded Fund as followed below.

Several emerging markets now trade ETFs; in addition, emerging market ETFs are also listed in foreign markets. Broad based emerging market ETFs were introduced almost ten years ago. ETF activity in Asia is quite limited relative to other regions. Japan, Hong Kong, Korea and Taiwan have the most ETF activity in Asia. Among the BRIC countries of Brazil, China, India and Russia, ETF activity is highest in China and Brazil, followed by India and barely exists in Russia. ETF activity is concentrated only in a few countries around the world.

The performance of ETFs and index funds was measured by comparing their daily returns with the returns of the underlying indices. The tracking error of ETFs and index funds was analysed to examine how closely the ETFs and mutual funds track their underlying indices. Tracking error was measured as the standard deviation of the difference between the returns of the underlying index and the returns of ETFs or index funds; this is similar to the approach adopted by Frino and Gallagher (2001). For reasons of brevity, a graphical representation of the returns and tracking error of GS Nifty BeES and UTI Index Fund alone are provided in the Appendix.

Traditionally, the performance of mutual funds was examined using Jensen's alpha. Hence, further analysis was done to check whether ETFs and index funds were able to generate better alphas. Jensen's alpha was used to measure the excess returns of a fund over that of its underlying index. The excess returns of a fund were regressed against the excess returns of its underlying index as shown below:

$$R_p - R_f = \alpha_i + \beta (R_m - R_f) + \epsilon_t$$

where R_p is the return of an ETF or an index fund; R_f is the risk-free return; α_i is the Jensen's alpha; β is the beta of the fund; and e_t is the error term. Jensen's alpha was calculated for those ETFs and index funds tracking either the S&P BSE SENSEX or the CNX Nifty index.

Performance of ETFs-

Schemes	Latest Price	Asset Size (Rs. cr.)	As on April-2016			
			3mth	6mth	1yr	2yr
Motilal MOST Shares NASDAQ 100 ETF	297.2	75.42	5.1	7.4	11.7	19.1
IIFL Nifty ETF		1.5	4.5	-3.4	10.7	21.5
GS Gold BeES	2,624.00	1,795.93	12.5	10	8.5	1.6
UTI Gold Exchange Traded Fund	2,617.00	498.17	12.6	10	8.4	1.2
IDBI Gold Exchange Traded Fund	2,738.80	104.77	12.5	10	8.4	1.5
Religare Invesco Gold ETF	2,595.01	0	12.5	9.9	8.3	0.7
SBI - ETF Gold	2,673.80	1,020.90	12.5	10	8.3	1.4
Birla Sun Life Gold ETF (G)	2,720.00	84.07	12.3	10	8.2	0.6
Kotak Gold ETF	259.15	521.76	12.5	9.9	8.2	1.3
Axis Gold ETF	2,640.00	245.39	12.4	9.8	8.2	1.3
ICICI Pru Gold ETF	97	125.43	12.6	10.1	8.2	1.4
Quantum Gold Fund	1,302.90	64.94	12.3	9.8	8.1	1.3
HDFC Gold Exchange Traded Fund	2,698.00	633.01	12.4	9.8	8	1.2
LIC NOMURA G-Sec LTE Fund - RP (G)	14.98	67.82	2.8	3.6	7.8	--
R*Shares Gold ETF	2,558.00	1,448.96	11.8	9.4	7.5	-0.6
Can Gold Exchange Traded Fund	2,690.00	84.8	11.2	9.2	6.5	-1.4
GS Liquid BeES	1,000.00	915.24	--	--	--	--
HDFC Sensex ETF	2,470.00	10.3	-0.2	--	--	--
Kotak NV 20 ETF		0.57	1	--	--	--
SBI - ETF Nifty 50	75.6	4,845.03	-0.4	-6.7	--	--
HDFC Nifty ETF		18.98	-0.4	--	--	--
UTI Sensex Exchange Traded Fund	248	12	-0.6	-7.4	--	--
Edelweiss ETS - Banking		0.8	-3.8	--	--	--

UTI Nifty Exchange Traded Fund		17.61	-0.3	-6.4	--	--
Edelweiss ETS - Nifty (Nifty EES)	*N.T	8.44	-0.4	-6.7	--	--
R*shares Consumption ETF		13.12	-2.3	-4	-4.3	13.2
Motilal MOST Shares Midcap 100 ETF	13.87	32.63	-4.1	-4	-5.3	21
Motilal Oswal MOST Shares Gold ETF	*N.T	29.66	-5.5	-4.1	-6.1	-7.5
SBI - ETF Nifty Next 50		9.62	-4.8	-6.4	-6.8	--
GS Shariah BeES	176	2.19	-0.5	-4.2	-7.2	7.7
GS Junior BeES	187.35	87.01	-5	-6.8	-7.6	16.5
ICICI Prudential CNX 100 ETF	97	22.83	-1.2	-6.7	-11.5	8
R*Shares Dividend ETF		10.82	-2	-5.3	-11.6	4
Birla Sun Life Nifty ETF		22.9	-0.4	-6.4	-11.8	6.7
SBI - ETF Sensex	257.8	1,392.12	-0.7	-7.6	-12	6.1
R*Shares Nifty ETF	80.3	24.24	-0.3	-6.7	-12.1	6.9
R*shares CNX 100 ETF	78.36	5.69	-1.3	-6.9	-12.1	7.7
ICICI Prudential Nifty ETF	81.25	353.77	-0.4	-6.7	-12.3	6.5
Kotak Nifty ETF	768	225.52	-0.4	-6.8	-12.3	6.1
SBI - ETF BSE 100	78.5	1.37	-1.1	-6.8	-12.5	--
Religare Invesco Nifty ETF		0	-0.4	-6.7	-12.5	6.2
ICICI Pru SPiCe Plan	290	4.01	-0.6	-7.4	-12.5	0.6
GS Nifty BeES	765.7	736.38	-0.5	-6.9	-12.6	5.9
Motilal MOST Shares M50 ETF	72.5	20.45	-0.6	-7.1	-12.9	3.7
Kotak Sensex ETF	253	9.39	-0.7	-7.7	-12.9	4.4
SBI - ETF Nifty Bank	75.6	82.52	-3.8	-11.2	-14.9	--
R*Shares Banking ETF	1,708.00	256.36	-3.8	-11.2	-15	10.4
Kotak Banking ETF		820.67	-3.8	-11.2	-15	--
GS Bank BeES	1,569.00	481.53	-3.9	-11.4	-15.2	9.7
GS Hang Seng BeES	2,150.00	5.06	-0.9	-7.2	-15.3	1.7
GS CPSE ETF	19.31	1,745.72	-8.2	-12.1	-23.2	-1.1
GS Infra BeES	250	12.69	-5.5	-15.2	-26.2	-3
GS PSU Bank BeES	259.24	21.16	-12.4	-27.5	-32.9	-9.5
Kotak PSU Bank ETF	238	14.26	-12.4	-27.5	-33	-11.6

Conclusion-

ETFs have grown tremendously during the last decade and have become a significant part of the equity market activity; hence, regulators are keeping a close watch on any potential impact of these products on financial stability and market volatility. In India, trading in ETFs has been quite limited relative to the U.S. and Europe. Only the 25% of ETFs affect the total turnover of National Stock Exchange and Bombay Stock Exchange. Emerging market regulators have been appropriately cautious in not allowing complex ETFs. In countries such as India, trading in ETFs has been quite limited relative to the U.S. and Europe. ETFs based on broad market indexes with sufficient liquidity appear to be suitable products for retail customers. Local regulators in emerging markets have typically allowed only simple ETFs in the local market. However, foreign providers can create and list complex ETFs in the foreign market. ETFs are one of the most successful products introduced on exchanges in recent years. Regulators will need to tread carefully to manage risks and yet not impose unnecessary regulation. There is little by way of data and facts concerning the risks of ETFs. Indian stock market regulators only play an important role in encouraging to trade ETFs in stock market and to create awareness about riskless, profitable ETFs to stock traders. And also Academic scholars can play a role by conducting comprehensive and unbiased analysis